

An Experimental Analysis of The Overall Heat Transfer Coefficient On Cross Flow Heat Exchanger & Fin Effectiveness

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ABSTRACT

As far modern requirement is to make a small car so there is an immediate need to design an effectively heated exchanger. In this paper, the impact of finned heated exchanger over a without finned heated exchanger on overall heated return coefficient is examined. The overall heated return coefficient is examined for both heated exchange with air rate 3m/s, 4m/s, 5m/s and 6m/s and coolant flow 180 Lit/hr, 260 Lit/ hr, 340 Lit/hr, 420 Lit/hr ad 500 Lit/hr. Finned-tube heated exchangers are common and important components in many energy methods Fin-and-tube heated exchangers are normally used in several sites such as warming, ventilating, refrigerator and air conditioning equipment methods The fin performance is often indicated with regards to heated return coefficient and fin performance, which is described as the number of heated return quantity with fin to heated return quantity in without fin heated exchanger. This case is the one providing the most heated return quantity because this suits the most generating prospective (temperature difference) for convection heated return. The research described in this provides a combined methodical, test and statistical analysis of Overall heated return coefficient of coolant as water by use of circular finned tube heated exchanger and without fin tube exchanger with forced convection. The nice and cosy return and pressure drop results for the pin fin heated exchanger were in comparison with the results for a smooth-pipe heated exchanger. The test system is very just like cars' air conditioning equipment system. The examines heated return coefficient, pressure drop, overall heated return coefficient with the finned tube heated exchanger and without finned tube heated exchanger. From the analysis, Finned-tube heated exchanger gives the overall heated return coefficient 14.07W/m²K.

Keywords: Finned Pipe Heat Exchanger; Water; Round Fin; Temperature; Overall Heat Exchange Coefficient; Performance

I. Introduction

Heated exchanger is a program, which used to modify warm energy between two fluids, between an excellent surface position and a fluid or between strong partials and a fluid. The demand high for small specifications warm exchanger program which improved due to their need in the implementing such as Automobiles, aerospace, etc.[1] An key elements affecting in warm return are Reynolds wide variety, fin dimension and fin place (pitch). Heated return can be effectively improved by handling these aspects. Reynolds wide variety, fin dimension, fin content, fin concept, fin dimension, in place are most effective aspects affect Heated Exchanger. The maximum heat return quantity was observed at 42000 Reynolds wide variety, 20 mm fin dimension [8] Round have a very wide position of the program. Finned-tube warm exchangers are common and vital elements in many energy techniques Fin-and-tube heat exchangers are commonly used on several websites such as heating, ventilating, refrigerator and air refresher systems[2]. In various programs warm from the bout is dissipated by natural as well as forced convection and radiation. Various types of bout are rectangle-shaped, rectangular shape, circular, annular and indicated or pin bout, to a combination of different geometries, have been used. These bouts may stick out from either a rectangular or circular system.[7] The fin performance is usually indicated in terms of comfort return coefficient and ineffectiveness, which is identified as the number of comfort return quantity with the fin to warm return quantity without fin warm exchanger. This case is the one providing the maximum warm return quantity because this suits the maximum driving potential (temperature difference) for the convection warm return. The goal of the fin is to increase the production of the position and heat return coefficient. [4] It is very useful in warm exchanger design or in the assessment of comfort exchanger performance if we know the fin performance. In many guides provided the fin performance made out of the following three assumptions: (a) ongoing fluid warm range, (b) reliable warm return coefficient, and (c) one-dimensional warm transmitting in the fin. However, most actual warm exchangers may not meet only one of these three logic. A lot of assessments have been performed to assess warm return coefficient of comfort exchanger having bout.[3]

The circular finned-tube offers are typically used in the areas. In order to enhance the air-side warm return performance of these offers, such as to increase the fin performance and compactness as well as peace problems, much medical execute has been done carefully [5] Heated return enhances as the position of the radiator set up is improved. So, do the car having inside better place, the manufacturers of professional vehicles have a large enhance of comfort release into the air refresher program and they change the geometry the contract of tube joints in vehicle radiator to increase the position for better warm return. The advance in a binding contract of tube joints in the radiator is taken out by verifying result of the content of tube.[6].

The present executes the result of a circular fin of Steel in the Heated exchanger is examined experimentally.

II. Experimental Setup

Fig.1 Schematic of the Experimental setup

The schematic plan of test set up as caved Figure:1, which used in this research, a Package Container with prospective 35liters, Warming device curls of 2kW heating perspective, a Centrifugal Force with Engine, a Rotameter with go 0 to 1000 LPH, an Electric inflator of Engine 5HP with Fan, Ongoing Duct, Heated variety Indication of 12 paths, Varies up-to 0~260 v, four Thermocouples go 0°c to 100°c., Heated variety Gun -50°c to 450°c, Manometer, U-Tube Manometer 0 to 250 mm of Hg, and Mixture Circulation Heated Exchanger specifications as per Table.

In this evaluate, a cross-flow warm exchanger (automobile radiator) which set up inside the ventilation path (constant duct) and its configurations is louvered fin and pipe type. Coolant as standard water as through pipe (10 passes) with combination place. The radiator of an engine was 50cm long and 50cm size as in fig. and they depend on 10 pipe joints. The radiator consists of round, pipe joints, higher and lower water hose, and the exterior front side place. All the 10 pipe joints were in a single row and each pipe was 8mm thicker.

S. No.	Title	Value
1	Fin Material	Aluminum
2	Tube Material	M.S

3	Tube Internal Diameter	0.013 m
4	Tube Outer Diameter	0.0146 m
5	Fin Outer Diameter	0.0343 m
6	Fin Thickness	0.001 m
7	Fin Space	0.03933 m
8	No. of Fins	900
9	No of Tube Pass	10
10	Total Length of Tube	0.5 m

Table 1. Specifications

III. Working out of Heating Exchanger

In these installation tests, the liquid streaming inside the pipe exchange heated to the outside air streaming in the ventilation route. The air-side and tube-side heat exchange rates can be measured as:

$$Q_a = \dot{m}_a C_{p,a} (T_{a,o} - T_{a,i}) \tag{1}$$

$$Q_f = \dot{m}_f C_{p,f} (T_{f,o} - T_{f,i}) \tag{2}$$

where Q_a and Q_f are heat transfer rates at the air and fluid flows respectively.

The arithmetic average of the heat transfer rate is:

$$Q_{avg} = 0.5 (Q_a - Q_f) \tag{3}$$

The performance of the heat exchanger is analyzed the conventional $\epsilon - NTU$ technique and the effectiveness, ϵ , is defined as:

$$\epsilon = \frac{Q_{avg}}{(\dot{m}C_p)_{min} (T_{f,i} - T_{a,i})} \tag{4}$$

The relationship of the effectiveness, the number of transfer unit (NTU), and the minimum capacity flow rate $(\dot{m}C_p)_{min}$ at the air-side could be:

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{C^*} [1 - e^{-(1-e^{-NTU})}] \tag{5}$$

$$NTU = \frac{UA}{(\dot{m}C_p)_{min}} \tag{6}$$

$$C^* = \frac{(\dot{m}C_p)_{min}}{(\dot{m}C_p)_{max}} \tag{7}$$

Using equations (5) and (6) the experimental overall heat transfer coefficient, UA could be evaluated.

IV. Result and Discussion

To calculate the effect of fin the various factors are like coolant huge, air circulation speed, warm and etc. The assess the truth of the dimensions played around with system is examined with water & the played around with Overall Heat Exchange Coefficient is in comparison with a standard connection Dittus-Boelter formula (for strong flow). The research outcome suits 0.60% with the different outcome.

Graphically Analysis of Overall Heat Exchange Coefficient with Various Parameters:

Fig.2 Variation of air side Reynolds number with velocity of air and water flow rate

In cross-flow heat exchanger For different velocities 3, 4, 5 and 6 m/s the chart of Airside Reynolds variety compared to quantity circulation amount of water is attracted as caved fig.2 the determine and their comparative evaluation studied.

Fig.3 Variation of water side Reynolds number with velocity of air and water flow rate

For different velocities 3, 4, 5 and 6 m/s the chart of Riverside Reynolds number compared to quantity circulation amount water is attracted as caved fig.3 the determine and their comparative evaluation studied

Fig.4 Variation of Overall heat transfer co-efficient (Experimentally) with velocity of air and water flow rate

For different velocities 3, 4, 5 and 6 m/s the graph of U experimentally versus volume flow rate of water is drawn below as shown in the figure.4 and their relative comparison studied

Fig.5 Variation of Overall heat transfer co-efficient with (Theoretically) velocity of air and water flow rate

For different velocities 3, 4,5 and 6 m/s the graph of Utheoretically versus volume flow rate of water is drawn as shown in the figure.5 and their relative comparison studied

Fig.6 Variation of fin effectiveness with velocity of air and water flow rate

For different velocities 3, 4, 5 and 6 m/s the graph of Fin effectiveness versus volume flow rate of water in lit/ hr, is drawn below as shown in the figure and their relative comparison studied.

Fig.7 Variation of Nusselt number with Reynolds number water side

For different velocities, 3, 4, 5 and 6 m/s the graph of water-side Nusselt number versus water-side Reynolds number is drawn below as shown in the figure.7 and their relative comparison studied

V. CONCLUSIONS

A complete set of statistical parameter research on automobile rad has been presented in details in this document. The computation has been carried out by well confirmed and confirmed ranking. The corresponding statistical ingredients have been temporarily described in the document. A first part of the parametric research has been concentrated on the impact of the situation on fluid(mass circulation amount, feedback parameters).

In Cross circulation heat exchanger research installation is a useful tool for examining different factors of finned pipe heat exchanger and heat loss related examining, it will carry the factors heat effects on heat range. The model will help define heat exchanger performance and offer a basis for evaluating current heat range managing situation. Category and Design details help to understand the important and commercial application of heat exchangers.

As shown in the graph we determine that the Overall heat exchange amount of finned pipe heat exchanger is greater than without finned pipe heat exchanger. Now as we increase the airspeed heat exchange amount of finned pipe warm exchanger is improves because the Reynolds variety improves the nusselt variety is also improves because nusselt variety is directly proportionate to the warm exchange coefficient. So, warm exchange amount improves.

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